

KAPUTO-FABRITSIO OPERATORI ISHTIROK ETGAN DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMA UCHUN NOLOKAL MASALA

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Abstract: Ushbu ishda vaqt o'zgaruvchisi bo'yicha Kaputo-Fabritsio operatori, fazoviy o'zgaruvchi bo'yicha esa Lejandr operatori qatnashgan xususiy hosilali differensial tenglama uchun nolokal shartli masalaning bir qiymatli yechilishi isbotlangan. Bunda Lejandr polinomlarining xossalariidan foydalanilgan

Keywords: Kaputo-Fabritsio operatori; nolokalshart; Lejandr polinomiali; Furye usuli.

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NONLOCAL PROBLEM DIFFERENTIAL EQUATION WITH CAPUTO- FABRIZIO OPERATOR

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Abstract: In this work a unique solvability of nonlocal boundary problem for partial differential equation involving Caputo-Fabrizio operator in time and Legendre operator in space-variable. Properties of Legendre polynomials have been used.

Keywords: Caputo-Fabrizio operator; nonlocal condition; Legendre polynomials; Fourier method.

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Diffuziya jarayonini aks ettiruvchi xususiy hosilali differensial tenglamalar uchun chegaraviy masalalarning bir qiymatli yechilishi ko'plab tadqiqotlarda isbotlangan [1-4].

Ushbu ishda oldingi ishlardan farqli ravishda vaqt o'zgaruvchisi bo'yicha Kaputo-Fabritsio integro-differensial operatori, fazoviy o'zgaruvchisi bo'yicha esa Lejandr operatori qo'llanilgan xususiy hosilali integro-differensial tenglama uchun nolokal shartli masala tadqiq etiladi. Bu operator qatnashgan tenglama uchun lokal masalalar [5] ishda tadqiq etilgan.

Masala. $\Omega = \{(x, t): 0 < x < 1, 0 < t < T\}$ sohada

$${}^{CF}D_{0t}^{\alpha}U(x, t) = [(1 - x^2)U_x]_x + f(x, t) \quad (1)$$

tenglama va

$$U(x,0) = U(x,\xi) + \varphi(x), \quad -1 \leq x \leq 1, \quad 0 \leq \xi \leq T \quad (2)$$

nolokal shartni qanoatlantiruvchi, hamda $x = -1, x = 1$ da $U(x,t), U_x(x,t)$ chegaralangan $U(x,t)$ funksiyani toping. Bu yerda

$${}^{CF}D_{0t}^\alpha g(t) = \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \int_0^t g'(s) e^{\frac{-\alpha}{1-\alpha}(t-s)} ds \quad (3)$$

$-0 < \alpha < 1$ tartibli Kaputo-Fabritsio operatori [6].

Dastlab $f(x,t) \equiv 0$ bo'lgan holda (1) tenglamaning yechimini $U(x,t) = \nu(t) \cdot X(x) \neq 0$ ko'rinishda qidiramiz. U holda (1) dan

$${}^{CF}D_{0t}^\alpha \nu(t) \cdot X(x) = [(1-x^2)X''(x) - 2xX'(x)]\nu(t)$$

ni olamiz. Bu tenglikni $\nu(t) \cdot X(x)$ ga bo'lsak

$$\frac{{}^{CF}D_{0t}^\alpha \nu(t)}{\nu(t)} = \frac{[(1-x^2)X''(x) - 2xX'(x)]}{X(x)} = -\lambda.$$

yoki

$${}^{CF}D_{0t}^\alpha \nu(t) + \lambda \nu(t) = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$(1-x^2)X''(x) - 2xX'(x) + \lambda X(x) = 0 \quad (5)$$

tenglamalar kelib chiqadi. $U(x,t), U_x(x,t)$ funksiyalarning $x = -1, x = 1$ da chegaralangan yechimga ega ekanligi ma'lum hamda bu yechim

$$X(x) = P_n(x) = \frac{1}{2^n \cdot n!} \cdot \frac{d^n(x^2-1)^n}{dx^n} \quad (n=0,1,2,\dots) \quad (6)$$

Lejandr polinomlari orqali ifodalanadi [7].

Ma'lumki [7], $P_n(x)$ ($n=0,1,2,\dots$) Lejandr polinomlari $[-1;1]$ da ortogonal sistema tashkil qiladi va $\|P_n(x)\|^2 = \frac{2}{2n+1}$.

Ihtiyoriy $[-1;1]$ da bo'lakli uzlukli $g(x)$ funksiyani $\{P_n(x)\}$ sistema bo'yicha Furye qatoriga yoyish mumkin [7]:

$$g(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_n P_n(x), \quad C_n = \frac{(g, P_n)}{\|P_n\|^2} = \frac{2n+1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 g(x) P_n(x) dx.$$

Bunday qatorlarni Furrye-Lejandr qatorlari deyiladi.

Masala yechimini Furrye-Lejandr qatori ko'rinishida qidiramiz:

$$u(x,t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \nu_n(t) P_n(x), \quad (7)$$

bu yerda $\nu_n(t)$ hozircha noma'lum funksiyalar.

Berilgan funksiyalar $f(x,t), \varphi(x)$ larni ham Furrye-Lejandr qatoriga yoyamiz:

$$f(x,t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_n(t) P_n(x), \quad (8)$$

$$\varphi(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \varphi_n P_n(x), \quad (9)$$

bu yerda

$$f_n(t) = \frac{2n+1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 f(x,t) P_n(x) dx, \quad \varphi_n = \frac{2n+1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \varphi(x) P_n(x) dx.$$

(7), (8) ni (1), (2) ga qo‘ysak t o‘zgaruvchiga nisbatan quyidagi masalani olamiz:

$$\begin{cases} {}^{CF}D_{0^+}^{\alpha} v_n(t) + n(n+1)v_n(t) = f_n(t), \\ v_n(0) = v_n(\xi) + \varphi_n. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

(10) masalaning yechimini topish uchun [5] da ko‘rilgan Koshi masalasi yechimidan foydalaniladi. Buning uchun $f_n(0) = n(n+1)v_n(0)$ shart bajarilishi talab etiladi, shunda

$$\begin{aligned} v_n(t) = & \frac{1-\alpha}{1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha)} f_n(t) + \frac{\alpha}{(1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha))^2} \int_0^t f_n(\xi) e^{\frac{-n(n+1)\alpha}{1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha)}(t-\xi)} d\xi + \\ & \frac{v_n(0)}{1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha)} e^{\frac{-n(n+1)\alpha}{1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha)}t} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

ifoda olinadi. Bundan $v_n(\xi)$ ni topib, so‘ngra $v_n(0) = v_n(\xi) + \varphi_n$ shartga ko‘ra (11) dagi noma‘lum o‘zgaruvchi $v_n(0)$ ni quyidagicha topamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} v_n(0) = & \frac{1}{1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha) - e^{\frac{-n(n+1)\alpha}{1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha)}\xi}} \left[(1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha))\varphi_n + (1-\alpha)f_n(\xi) - \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{\alpha}{1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha)} \int_0^{\xi} f_n(s) e^{\frac{-n(n+1)\alpha}{1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha)}(\xi-s)} ds \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

(7) cheksiz qatorning tekis yaqinlashishini isbotlash uchun dastlab (12) ifoda uchun, so‘ngra esa (11) ifoda uchun baho olamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} |v_n(0)| \leq & |\varphi_n| + \frac{C_1 |f_n(\xi)|}{1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha)}, \\ |v_n(t)| \leq & \frac{|\varphi_n|}{1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha)} + \frac{C_2 |f_n(\xi)|}{(1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha))^2} + \frac{|f_n(t)|}{1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha)}. \end{aligned}$$

Ushbu baholar (7) cheksiz qatorning tekis yaqinlashishini isbotlashda unga majorant bo‘lgan qatorning yaqinlashishini isbotlash uchun muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Haqiqatdan ham, agar $\varphi(x), f(x,t)$ funksiyalar o‘z aniqlanish sohasida uzluksiz bo‘lsa

$$|u(x,t)| \leq \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} |v_n(t)| |P_n(x)| \leq \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{C}{n^2} < \infty$$

baho o‘rinli. Tenglamada ishtirok etadigan $u_x, u_{xx}, {}^{CF}D_{0t}^{\alpha}u$ funksiyalarga mos keluvchi cheksiz qatorlarning tekis yaqinlashishini isbotlashda berilgan $\varphi(x), f(x,t)$ funksiyalarga ko‘proq shart tushishi tabiiy. Bunda [8] da

ko‘rsatilganidek hisoblashlar asosida $|g_n| \leq \frac{4\sqrt{2}}{(2n-3)^{3/2}} \|g\|$ tengsizliklardan

foydalansak, berilgan funksiyalarning uzluksizlikdan tashqari, x o‘zgaruvchi bo‘yicha 2-tartibli hosilalari kvadrati bilan jamlanuvchi bo‘lishi sharti ham qo‘yiladi. Masala yechimi yagonaligi esa Furrye-Lejandr qatorlari nazariyasiga ko‘ra Lejandr polinomlarining to‘la ortonormal Sistema tashkil qilishidan foydalanib isbotlanadi. Demak, quyidagi tasdiq o‘rinli:

Teorema. Agar $\varphi(x), f(x,t)$ funksiyalar o‘z aniqlanish sohasida uzluksiz va x o‘zgaruvchi bo‘yicha 2-tartibli hosilalari kvadrati bilan jamlanuvchi bo‘lsa hamda

$$f_n(0) = \frac{n(n+1)}{1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha) - e^{\frac{-n(n+1)\alpha}{1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha)}\xi}} \left[(1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha))\varphi_n + (1-\alpha)f_n(\xi) - \frac{\alpha}{1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha)} \int_0^{\xi} f_n(s) e^{\frac{-n(n+1)\alpha}{1+n(n+1)(1-\alpha)}(\xi-s)} ds \right]$$

shart bajarilsa, u holda masalaning yagona yechimi mavjud va u (7) ko‘rinishda ifodalanadi.

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